

Catalytic effect of AOT/heptane and CTAB/CHCl₃/hexane reverse micelles on the fading of rosaniline hydrochloride by periodate

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Abstract : The kinetics of fading of rosaniline hydrochloride (RA⁺) by periodate (IO₄⁻) was studied in two different reverse micellar systems AOT/heptane and CTAB/CHCl₃/hexane. The reaction between RA⁺ and IO₄⁻ obeys first order kinetics with respect to RA⁺ and IO₄⁻ in both the reverse micellar media. In the AOT system, the pseudo-first order rate constant was found to be fifteen times greater than in aqueous medium, while in the CTAB reverse micellar system the rate increases by three hundred times. The significant increase in reverse micelles is attributed to the unique properties of the water pools. The study was carried at different surfactant concentrations and different *W* (= [H₂O]/[Surfactant]) values. The Berezin pseudo phase model was used to explain the effect of surfactant. The activation parameters determined in the presence of reverse micelles and aqueous medium also account for the large acceleration in the presence of reverse micelles.

Keywords : AOT, CTAB, reverse micelles, water pool, rosaniline hydrochloride.

Introduction

When surfactants aggregate in non polar solvents forming reverse micelles, their polar or charged groups are located in the interior or core of the aggregate while their hydrocarbon tails extend into the bulk solvent. Water is readily solubilised in the polar core called "water pool" which exhibits unique properties characterised by a parameter, $W \{ = ([H_2O]/[Surfactant]) \}^1$. At low water contents $W \leq 5$, the water is structured due to interactions with the polar head groups and counter ions. When $W > 12$ unstructured 'free' water appears. The properties of the structured water are different from free water. For example, the solubilising capacities of the two pseudo phases are different; the structured water has comparatively low dielectric constant, low mobility and a high ionic strength (due to the counter ions in the case of ionic surfactants). The pH experienced by a species is also dependent on *W* and the type of surfactant used, hence pK_a of charged species changes in the water pools. We

have earlier studied the aquation of tris-2,2'-bipyridyl iron(II), base hydrolysis of tris-1,10'-phenanthroline iron(II) and oxidation of iodide by V^V in the presence of CTAB reverse micelles²⁻⁴. In this work, we have carried out a kinetic study of the fading of rosaniline hydrochloride (RA⁺) by (IO₄⁻) in two types of reverse micellar systems, anionic-AOT/heptane and cationic-CTAB/CHCl₃/hexane. The results are reported.

Results and discussion

Fading of RA⁺ by IO₄⁻ in AOT/heptane and CTAB/chloroform/hexane : The reaction between RA⁺ and IO₄⁻ in both the reverse micellar media obey first order kinetics with respect to RA⁺ as observed by the linear plots between log (absorbance) versus time under the conditions $\{ [RA^+] \ll [IO_4^-] \}$. The pseudo-first order rate constant is directly proportional to $[IO_4^-]$ indicating first order kinetics with respect to IO₄⁻ (Tables 1, 2). Based on the results obtained from kinetic studies and the stoi-

Table 1. Effect of varying periodate, $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ on observed first order rate constant (k_0) at $W = 6.0$ and $W = 10.0$

$[\text{RA}^+] = 7.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}, [\text{CTAB}] = 0.1 \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}, T = 29 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$10^3 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$W = 6.0$		$W = 10.0$	
	$10^2 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 \times k_0$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^2 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 \times k_0$ (s ⁻¹)
0.620	6.90	8.10	3.44	10.1
1.20	13.3	16.0	6.60	18.9
1.87	20.7	24.1	10.4	33.0
2.50	27.7	31.0	13.8	37.3
3.30	36.6	42.0	18.3	49.0
4.20	-	-	23.3	57.0
5.80	-	-	32.2	85.0

Table 2. Effect of varying periodate, $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ on observed first order rate constant (k_0) at $W = 6.0$ and $W = 10.0$

$[\text{RA}^+] = 7.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, [\text{AOT}] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, T = 29 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$10^3 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$W = 6.0$		$W = 10.0$	
	$10^2 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 \times k_0$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^2 \times [\text{IO}_4^-]_e$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 \times k_0$ (s ⁻¹)
0.470	4.40	0.390	2.60	0.250
0.940	8.70	0.620	5.20	0.460
1.87	17.3	1.43	10.4	0.770
2.80	25.9	1.60	15.5	0.960
3.74	34.6	2.00	20.7	1.69

chiometry determined by mole ratio method the mechanism given in Scheme 1 is proposed.

Effect of variation of W and AOT in the presence of AOT/heptane :

The reaction is markedly accelerated in the presence of both AOT and CTAB reverse micelles. The significant increase in the presence of reverse micelles is due to the unique properties of the solubilised water of reverse micelles like low micro polarity and high ionic strength. The pseudo-first order rate constant k_0 and second order rate constant k_2 have been determined over a W range 5–12 at constant $[\text{AOT}]$ and the study has been repeated at different concentrations of AOT (Table 3). At constant $[\text{AOT}]$, k_0 decreases with W and also decreases with increase in concentration AOT. This is because of two reasons (i) RA^+ being hydrophobic and by electrostatic interactions gets attached to the surfactant chains irrespective of the size of the water pool. The IO_4^- is present in the aqueous water pool because it is repelled by dioctyl sulfosuccinate, DOS^- group of AOT. For small W , the probability of IO_4^- being nearer to RA^+ is more since the movement of is restricted. As W increases, is present in the central aqueous water pool and less vulnerable to attack by the RA^+ which is left at the interface. (ii) At low W , most of the water present is bound and at $W > 4$,

Scheme 1

Table 3. Effect of AOT and *W* on observed first order (*k*₀) and second order rate constants (*k*₂)

[RA ⁺] ₀ = 7.9 × 10 ⁻⁶ mol dm ⁻³ , [IO ₄ ⁻] ₀ = 1.87 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , T = 29 °C					
[AOT] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Na ⁺] _e (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ × <i>f</i> (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>W</i>	10 ⁵ × <i>k</i> ₀ (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ × <i>k</i> ₂ (mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
0.05	6.94	7.20	8.00	2.20	8.46
	5.55	9.00	10.0	1.81	8.57
	4.63	10.8	12.0	1.53	8.80
0.1	11.1	9.00	5.00	1.60	7.70
	9.26	10.8	6.00	1.43	8.09
	6.94	14.4	8.00	0.960	7.44
	5.55	18.0	10.0	0.770	7.20
	4.63	21.6	12.0	0.630	7.24
0.2	11.1	18.0	5.00	0.770	7.40
	9.26	21.6	6.00	0.650	7.47
	6.94	28.8	8.00	0.520	7.28
	5.55	36.0	10.0	0.410	7.69
	4.63	43.2	12.0	0.320	7.39

‘free’ water appears⁸. At low *W*, dielectric constant is less which favours a cation-anion reaction like the present one. Since the reaction obeys first order kinetics with respect to [IO₄⁻], the second order rate constant is calculated as $k_2 = k_0/[IO_4^-]_e$ and given in Table 3. It can be seen that *k*₂ is nearly constant for all values of *W* for all concentrations of AOT. The constancy is explained as follows : As *W* increases ionic strength decreases and dielectric constant increases. These two have opposing effects on the rate of the cation-anion reaction and their effects cancel each other. Therefore only concentration effect exists and it is the only factor responsible for acceleration.

Effect of W and CTAB in the presence of CTAB/CHCl₃/hexane/water :

The rate of the reaction increases around three hundred times more than in the aqueous medium while the rate increases only by fifteen times in the presence of AOT reverse micelles. Larger increase of rate in CTAB micelles is attributed to the existence of electrostatic interactions between IO₄⁻ and CTA⁺ in addition to the special properties. Table 4 shows that at constant [CTAB] both *k*₀ and *k*₂ increase with *W*. At low *W*, the reaction being a cation-anion reaction is facilitated by lower micropolarity of structured water. At the same time, with increase in *W*, ionic strength decreases which favours a cation-anion reaction (in the case of ionic surfactants, the

value of *W* regulates the concentration of CTA⁺ polar heads of the surfactant and its counter ions, Br⁻ in the aqueous water pool and therefore *W* gives the value of ionic strength (*μ*)⁹. At higher *W* (>6) micro polarity becomes closer to water and its effect is not significant. The acceleration of the reaction is only due to decrease in ionic strength with increase in *W*. Therefore the effect of *W* has been assessed in terms of ionic strength relating the rate constant *k*₂

$$k_2 = k_2^0 \frac{\gamma_{RA^+} \cdot \gamma_{IO_4^-}}{\gamma_{\#}} \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_{IO_4^-}$, γ_{RA^+} and $\gamma_{\#}$ are the activity coefficients of IO₄⁻, RA⁺ and the transition state complex and *k*₂⁰ is the rate constant at zero ionic strength. According to Guggenheim equation, the activity coefficient γ_i of an ion is related to ionic strength (*μ*).

$$-\log \gamma_i = \frac{AZ_i^2 \mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} - \sum_j B_{i,j} \cdot {}_jC_j \quad (2)$$

where *A* is equal to 0.5, *Z*_{*i*} is the charge on the ions and the summation for specific interaction term (*B*_{*i,j*}) extending over all ions of concentration *C*_{*j*}. In the present case, there are two kinds of specific interactions. One between the positively charged micellar surface, M and IO₄⁻ which is represented by *B*_{M,IO₄⁻}. The other interaction is between RA⁺ and the counter ion Br⁻ represented by

Table 4. Effect of CTAB and W on observed first order (k_0) and second order rate constants (k_2)

[RA ⁺] ₀ = 7.9 × 10 ⁻⁶ mol dm ⁻³ , [IO ₄ ⁻] ₀ = 1.87 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , T = 29 °C					
[CTAB] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Br ⁻] _e (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ × f (volume fraction)	W	10 ⁵ × k_0 (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ × k_2 (mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
0.05	6.94	7.20	8.00	27.6	10.6
	5.56	9.00	10.0	31.0	14.9
	4.63	10.8	12.0	40.0	23.1
	3.97	12.6	14.0	42.0	28.4
	3.47	14.4	16.0	58.0	38.8
0.1	16.7	6.00	3.33	17.7	5.80
	11.1	9.00	5.00	24.0	11.6
	9.26	10.8	6.00	25.0	14.5
	6.94	14.4	8.00	26.5	20.4
	5.56	18.0	10.0	28.8	27.9
	4.63	21.6	12.0	33.0	37.9
	3.97	25.2	14.0	38.2	51.6
	3.47	28.8	16.0	39.5	60.8
0.2	33.3	6.00	1.66	8.73	2.78
	16.7	12.0	3.33	15.4	9.90
	11.1	18.0	5.00	20.0	19.2
	9.26	21.6	6.00	22.0	25.3
	6.94	28.8	8.00	23.1	36.0
	5.56	36.0	10.0	24.2	46.5
	4.63	43.2	12.0	26.2	61.0
	3.97	50.4	14.0	28.8	78.0
	3.47	57.6	16.0	31.5	100
	0.3	50.0	6.00	1.11	2.02
33.3		8.90	1.66	4.41	2.50
16.7		18.0	3.33	14.6	14.2
11.1		27.0	5.00	18.8	27.2
9.26		32.4	6.00	20.5	35.3
6.94		43.2	8.00	22.6	51.4
5.56		54.0	10.0	23.7	66.6
4.63		64.8	12.0	25.1	86.6
3.97		75.6	14.0	26.4	91.0
3.47		86.4	16.0	27.6	145

$B_{RA^+Br^-}$. Using eqs. (1) and (2), it can be shown that

$$\log k_2 = \log k_2^0 - \frac{\mu^{1/2}}{1 + \mu^{1/2}} + b[Br^-]_e \quad (3)$$

where $b = (B_{M,IO_4^-/N}) + (B_{RA^+,Br^-})$

A plot of $\log k_2$ versus $[Br^-]_e \{=\mu\}$ was found to be linear at different concentrations of CTAB (Fig. 1) and the specific interaction effect included in the value of 'b'

represents the slope of plot between $\log k_2$ and $[Br^-]_e$. The value of 'b' was found to be -0.071, -0.074 and -0.070 for 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 mol dm⁻³ CTAB respectively. Since there is effect of W on rate even at $W = 16$ the value of 'b' includes the specific interaction effect of both the interface and water pool components.

At constant W , with increase in CTAB concentration, the second order rate constant increases. This study has been carried out in a detailed manner at $W (=3.33, 10.0,$

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength on fading of rosaniline hydrochloride by periodate at different concentrations of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 M CTAB.

16.0). The effect of CTAB concentration on rate constant can be explained by the Berezin pseudo phase model^{10,11} and according to this model, the second order rate constant k_2 is given by

$$k_2 = \frac{k_m P_{RA^+} K_{IO_4^-} C + k_w (1 - CV)}{(1 + K_{IO_4^-} C)(1 + K_{RA^+} C)} \quad (4)$$

In the above equation, k_m is the rate constant of the reaction at the micellar interface, k_w is the rate constant in the water pool, C is the concentration of CTAB, V is the molar volume of CTAB. The factors CV and $1-CV$ represent the fractions by volume of micellar and aqueous phases respectively. K_{RA^+} , $K_{IO_4^-}$ are the binding constants of rosaniline and periodate and are related to partition coefficients, P_{RA^+} and $P_{IO_4^-}$ by the equation, $K_{RA^+} = P_{RA^+}/V$, and $K_{IO_4^-} = P_{IO_4^-}/V$. In eq. (4), CV can be neglected in comparison to 1 and since IO_4^- is strongly bound to the micellar surface while RA^+ is weakly repelled, 1 can be considered much greater than $(K_{RA^+}) \cdot C$. Also there is an increase in rate with $[CTAB]$, therefore k_m is greater than k_w . The above equation now becomes

$$k_2 = \frac{k_m P_{RA^+} K_{IO_4^-} C}{(1 + K_{IO_4^-} C)} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{1}{k_m P_{RA^+} K_{IO_4^-} C} + \frac{1}{k_m K_{RA^+}} \quad (6)$$

If above equation holds good, a plot of $1/k_2$ versus $1/C$ should be linear and such a plot was obtained showing

the validity of Berezin pseudo phase model to reverse micelles (Fig. 2). The values of $K_{IO_4^-}$ were calculated at three values of W , 3.33, 10.0 and 16.0 from the slope and intercept using eq. (6); the values are 10.02, 3.10 and 1.98 respectively. The values show that the binding constant $K_{IO_4^-}$ of periodate with micellar interface decreases with increasing W . This is in agreement with the fact that at low W values the negative periodate is bound to the cationic interface by electrostatic forces. As the size of water pools increase the water soluble periodate goes more into the bulk water decreasing the binding constant.

Fig. 2. A plot of $1/k_2$ versus $1/C$ at various W values.

Activation parameters :

The temperature effect on the structural properties of a reverse micelle has been studied by Lang *et al.* They reported a 25–35% decrease in the radius of the droplet for a temperature increase of 35 °C¹². Thus change in temperature alters the structure of a reverse micelle which influences the kinetics of reactions. In the present study the temperature variation was 24–34 °C, hence very little structural changes can be expected. Good linear plots were obtained for Arrhenius equation (Figs. 3 and 4) and the activation parameters derived from Arrhenius and Eyring equation are shown in Table 5. The activation energies are much lower in CTAB, followed by AOT reverse micelles compared to aqueous medium. This is also a proof for the accelerating effects in the reverse micelles. The enthalpy, entropy and free energy of activation also show the same trend.

Fig. 3. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ at two different W 's in the presence of AOT.

Fig. 4. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ at two different W 's in the presence of CTAB.

Table 5. Activation parameters for the reaction between RA^+ and IO_4^-

	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Water	116.6	114.04	76.20	94.49
CTAB (0.1)				
$W = 5.0$	72.07	73.54	-55.91	90.42
$W = 10.0$	56.25	50.45	-116.01	85.45
AOT (0.1)				
$W = 6.0$	76.15	75.69	-48.44	89.51
$W = 10.0$	91.29	85.42	-23.35	92.56

Experimental

Materials :

Stock solutions of rosaniline hydrochloride (BDH), sodium periodate (Merck, India) were prepared in doubly distilled water. Chloroform, hexane and heptane were distilled before use. CTAB (Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide; from Merck, India) and AOT (Aerosol-T; from Sigma-Aldrich) were used as purchased without further purification. A 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution of the surfactant was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of CTAB in chloroform-hexane (3 : 2 v/v) mixture and AOT in heptane.

Kinetic measurement :

The kinetic study of fading of RA^+ by IO_4^- was carried out using a Shimadzu UV-1800 double beam spectrophotometer by measuring the decrease in absorbance of RA^+ at a wave length of 555 nm. The reaction was carried out at a temperature of 29 °C under pseudo-first order condition, $[IO_4^-] \gg [RA^+]$. The concentration of RA^+ was $7.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and that of IO_4^- was varied from 0.47×10^{-3} to $5.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The kinetic data are the averages from triplicate runs with reproducibility less than $\pm 5\%$. The pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained from the linear fit of \log (absorbance) versus time.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined in both the reverse micellar systems, AOT/heptane and CTAB/chloroform/hexane by spectrophotometry using mole ratio method, keeping the concentration of the rosaniline hydrochloride constant at $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and varying the concentration of IO_4^- from 0.5×10^{-5} to $50 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 555 \text{ nm}$ after the reaction has gone to completion over a period of 48 h (the absorbance corresponding to unreacted rosaniline). The mole ratio corresponding to the intersection point from the plot of absorbance versus mole ratio ($[RA^+]/[IO_4^-]$) indicates that one mole of the dye was consumed by one mole of periodate in both the reverse micellar systems. Similar results were reported by Babatunde⁵.

Product analysis :

The product analysis was carried out by mixing equimolar amount of dye and IO₄⁻. After the completion of the reaction a colourless solution indicating destruction of the quinonoid group was obtained and the UV-Visible spectrum of the product showed no absorption peak at $\lambda_{\max} = 555$ nm. The other product, IO₃⁻, was confirmed qualitatively through the starch-indicator test for liberated I₂ when KI was added to the reaction mixture at the end of the reaction⁶.

Preparation of the reverse micellar system and initiation of the reaction :

A typical experiment was carried out as follows : 0.015 × 10⁻³ dm³ of 5.27 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ aqueous rosaniline hydrochloride solution was injected into 10 × 10⁻³ dm³ of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ surfactant solution using a micro pipette. 0.045 × 10⁻³ dm³ of 0.415 mol dm⁻³ periodate was then added to initiate the reaction. These mixtures were shaken sufficiently to obtain a transparent and apparently homogenous solution that can be regarded as a reverse micellar system. In the case of CTAB system, the molar ratio of [Water] to [CTAB] i.e. *W* was varied in the range 1.33–16.0 and in the AOT system from 5.0 to 12.0.

Calculation of the effective concentrations in reverse micelles :

In the study of reactions in reverse micelles involving water-soluble reactants, the reactivity in the aqueous droplets of the reverse micelle is usually compared with that in bulk aqueous medium. In the case of first order reactions the measured rate constants may be compared directly in the two types of systems. However, in the case of bimolecular processes taking place in the water pools or at the interface of the reverse micelles, the calculation of second order rate constant involves the consideration of effective concentration of the reactants. The effective concentration of a reactant in the water pool is calculated by dividing the overall concentration by the volume fraction of solubilised water, *f* (= volume of aqueous phase/total volume of the solution)⁷. The volume fractions lie in the range 6.00 to 28.8 × 10⁻³ for 0.1 mol dm⁻³ CTAB. Hence there is a 166.63 to 34.70 fold increase in concen-

trations. For example, if the concentration of CTAB is 0.1 mol/L and *W* = 6.00 then *f* = (0.108/10). If [IO₄⁻]₀ = 1.87 × 10⁻³ then { [IO₄⁻]_e = [IO₄⁻]₀/*f* } = { 1.87 × 10⁻³ / 0.0108 } = 0.173 mol dm⁻³. The subscript 'o' is used to represent overall concentration and subscript 'e' to represent effective concentrations.

Conclusion

The reaction is markedly accelerated in the presence of both AOT and CTAB reverse micelles. The significant increase in the presence of reverse micelles is attributed to the unique properties of the solubilised water of reverse micelles like low micro polarity and high ionic strength, while the rate constant was found to be fifteen times greater in AOT compared to aqueous medium, the rate increases by three hundred times in CTAB reverse micelles. Large increase of rate in CTAB micelles is attributed to the existence of electrostatic interactions between IO₄⁻ and CTA⁺ in addition to the special properties. The effect of variation of *W* and [Surfactant] on rate was explained in terms of concentration effect in AOT reverse micelles and in terms of ionic strength effect in CTAB.

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